

Pull and Push Factors for Tourists to Choose Wellness Tourism in Bali

Eling Spirit

Putu Indah Budiapsari, I Gusti Agung Ngurah Wasudewa Wikananda, Made Indra
Wijaya

Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Warmadewa University, Jalan Terompong no.24 Denpasar, Bali-
Indonesia

Correspondence: putuindah51@yahoo.com

Abstract

Wellness tourism is a tourist activity that nowadays become a popular in society as an alternative for carrying out non-pharmacological therapy to achieve body balance, mind and spirit. Bali is a popular destination that provides several wellness activities such as SPA, yoga and meditation. This research aims to analyse the pull and push factors for tourists in choosing wellness tourism in Bali. Designed with descriptive research, this research uses a questionnaire method for collecting data. This measuring indicators in this questionnaire use a Likert scale. This study adopted a questionnaire that existed in previous research. The location of this research was carried out in Gianyar Regency, namely Bali Eling Spirit. The results of this study showed that the characteristics of the subjects based on gender were dominated by 56 women (70%) and men (30%). The majority of respondents were from Jakarta, totalling 55 (68.75%) and 25% of respondents worked as civil servants, totalling 20 people. Yoga is the type of wellness that is most frequently practiced by respondents, totalling 28 (70%) with a cost of 100 thousand-500 thousand rupiah (55%). The reason respondents chose wellness tourism in Bali was because of the various types of wellness. The SPSS analysis test results show that the pull and push factors got high scores with a total percentage of almost 100% means both factors are in the high category.

Keywords: Wellness tourism, pull factors, push factors, tourist

INTRODUCTION

Wellness tourism is a tourist activity that is well known by the public as an alternative effort to carry out non-pharmacological therapy, namely to achieve balance in the body, mind and spirit. Wellness tourism has several activities that tourists can choose such as SPA (Solus Per Aqua), yoga, hot springs, thalassotherapy, and many others. Wellness tourism is a sub-sector of health tourism that exist and being an interesting tourism activity in the world. (1) Global data shows that income from wellness tourism increased from 536 billion dollars in 2015 to 639 billion dollars in 2017 or an increase of around 6.5% per year and is expected to increase faster until 2022 reaching 919 billion dollars (2). Asia-

Pacific is the continent with the highest number of wellness tourism visits. This is supported by data showing that 2 Asian countries, China and India, added around 17 million to 22 million health trips from 2015 to 2017 (3). Therefore, Asia is a good destination choice for wellness tourism at this time. Indonesia is also one of the Asian countries with popular tourist destinations and wellness tourism and also be an interesting phenomenon in Indonesia especially in Bali (4). Bali is one of destination in wellness tourism in the SPA sector where Bali provides more than 20 of the best SPAs in the world (4). This is an attraction for tourists to try Balinese SPA accompanied by natural tourism, culture and customs that are still

maintained. Based on the high number of tourist visits and Bali's superiority in SPA, this could have the potential to increase income in the wellness tourism sector. Currently there is no data available about wellness tourism in Indonesia, especially in Bali, including the factors that make Bali Eling Spirit (6).

METHODS

In this research the author used a questionnaire to collect primary data which would then be analysed and described based on pull and push factors. The population of this research is Indonesian citizens who previously visited Bali Eling Spirit for wellness tourism or had never visited wellness tourism (7-8). This research will be carried out at Bali Eling Spirit, which is one of the places for wellness tourism in Gianyar Regency. The sample in this study used a total sampling of 80. The inclusion criteria of this research are Indonesian citizens aged

This research lasted for 3 months, from August to October 2023. Based on the table, the total sample amounted to 80 people. The characteristics of respondents who are female are 56 people (70%) and 24 people (30%) are male. This number is obtained by groups who have done wellness tourism as many as 40 people (50%), and have never done wellness tourism as many as 40 people (50%). Based on monthly income, 75 (92.6%) respondents earned 0-5 million rupiah, 4 (4.9%) 5-15 million rupiah, and 1 (1.2%) 15-30 million rupiah. The duration used to

tourists interested in visiting wellness tourism (5). Therefore, the author wants to research and analysing the pull and push factors that influence tourists' interest in choosing wellness tourism in Bali, especially in Gianyar Regency, namely

This type of research is descriptive research which was carried out in August-October 2023.

above 17 years or already have a ID card and willing to take part in the research and fill out the questionnaire by giving informed consent. The exclusion criteria of this research are questionnaire data is not completed yet, the interview has not yet been completed, not willing to take part in research. Questionnaires will be distributed directly over a 3-month period from August to October 2023. Data collection was carried out using g-forms and paper forms due to limited use of cell phones at the research location.

RESULTS

do wellness tourism in Bali by respondents is obtained with the average duration spent is 105 minutes. All respondents are Indonesian citizens who come from several regions in Indonesia. Based on the table, most of them came from Jakarta, 55 people (68.75%), Surabaya 3 people (3.75%), Tangerang 3 people (3.75%), Jember 1 person (1.25%), Bandung 2 people (2.5%), Medan 2 people (2.5%), Bali 14 people (17.5%). The occupation of respondents with the largest percentage is civil servants 20 people (25%), students 17 people

(21,25%), not working 17 people
(21,25%), self-employed 10 people

(12,5%) and administrative staff 6 people
(7,5%).

Variable	N
Sex	
Female	56 (70%)
Male	24 (30%)
Monthly income	75
0-5 million	(92,6%)
5-15 million	4 (4,9%)
15-30 million	1 (1,2%)
Duration of wellness	40 (100%)
Experience of wellness	
Have done wellness	40 (50%)
Never done wellness	40 (50%)
Region	
Jakarta	55
Surabaya	(68,75%)
Tangerang	3 (3,75%)
Jember	3 (3,75%)

Age	80 (100%)
Bandung	1 (1,25%)
Medan	2 (2,5%)
Bali	2 (2,5%)
	14
	(17,5%)
Occupation	
Civil Servant	20 (25%)
Self-Employed	10
	(12,5%)
Doctor	3 (3,75%)
Nurse	1 (1,25%)
Student	17
Dosen	(21,25%)
Bank	1 (1,25%)
Employees	1 (1,25%)
	6 (7,5%)
Administrative staff	3 (3,75%)
Contract	1 (1,25%)
Worker	17
Staff	(21,25%)
Not working	

Based on the results of this research, the place where most respondents to do wellness tourism is in Gianyar with the type of wellness that they done the most is SPA. Costs spent ranged from 100

thousand rupiah to 500 thousand rupiah for wellness tourism.

The biggest reason tourists or respondents choose wellness tourism in Bali is because of the various types of wellness and the natural beauty of Bali.

Variable	N	%	Average±SD
Push Score	80	100%	58,96 ± 5,87
High	80	100%	
Low	0	0%	

Push Score	80	100%	26,15 ± 3,29
High	79	98,8%	
Low	1	1,3%	
Total	80	100%	85,11 ± 7,01

Based on the table above, the results shows that the push variable gets a total score of 80 (100%) and the pull variable gets a score of 79 (98.8%). These two

variables get high results which is almost 100%, with a total interest score that is also high, 80 (100%). This states that there is high interest by tourists in both push and

pull factors in choosing wellness tourism in Bali Eling Spirit.

Variable	N	%
Location		
Gianyar	22	55%
Type of Wellness		
Yoga/Meditation	28	70%
Cost		
Rp. 100.000-500.000	22	55%

Based on the table above, the characteristics of wellness tourism are obtained which are divided based on location, type of wellness tourism, and costs spent on conducting wellness tourism. The largest location for wellness tourism is Gianyar Regency with 22 (55%), the most popular type of wellness is meditation with 28 (70%), and the costs that used for this wellness are mostly around 100.000 rupiah - 500.000 rupiah.

Reason	Amount
Various types of wellness	11
Natural Beauty of Bali	10
Healing	7

Based on the table above, the biggest reason why tourists or respondents choose wellness tourism in Bali is because of the various types of wellness with 11 people, 10 people from the natural beauty of Bali, followed by 7 people want to heal themselves.

DISCUSSION

Based on gender, the results obtained in this study were that female most likely to travel and do wellness tourism in Bali

Eling Spirit. Female prefer to undertake tourist activities regardless of age and women plan more trip details, recommend tourist destinations to friends or relatives and enjoy going on tourist trips with other female friends. Based on monthly income, this research found that the largest category was 0-5 million rupiah, amounting to 75 (92.6%). This income is included in the lower middle-income category with tourism activities such as shopping, refreshing and exercising. The largest number of domiciles of the tourists or respondents in this study was Jakarta, which is 55 people (68.75%). According to The Least and Most Stressful Cities Index 2021, Jakarta is one of the cities with high levels of stress (9-11). This has resulted in workers in the city of Jakarta taking tourist trips as an effort to relieve stress from daily activities or what is known as healing. Profession is one of the factors for traveling, including doing wellness tourism. This is how to eliminate stress that comes from work environment. In this study, the results of the work with the largest percentage were civil servants, numbering 20 (25%). This is in line with research by Hermawan (2022) which shows that civil servants have the opportunity to experience work stress caused by internal factors and external factors (12-15).

The results of this research showed that the biggest reason why tourists choose wellness tourism in Bali is because of the various types of wellness in Bali, and Bali's natural beauty (16-18). Pull factors have a positive and significant influence on tourists' interest in returning to wellness tourism in Bali, while push factors have an insignificant influence on

tourists' interest in returning to wellness tourism in Bali (19-21).

Work or profession is one of the factors for traveling, including doing wellness tourism. This is done to eliminate stress that arises in the work environment. In this study, the results of the work with the largest percentage were civil servants, numbering 20 (25%). Civil servants have the opportunity to experience work stress. Stress levels in civil servants are triggered by internal and external factors. Internal factors such as age, length of service, personality type, role conflict, and individual roles in the organization while external factors such as workload, work pressure, work environment, and social support (22-25).

The potentiation for wellness tourism in Bali focuses more on natural resources, spirituality, traditions and culture, and local wisdom. The research also found that the form of wellness tourism that needs to be developed is wellness tourism which is characteristic of Bali, for example natural beauty by involving the local community as a whole, and prioritizing the principles of sustainable tourism (26). These findings are in line with this research which found that natural beauty is the biggest reason for tourists to choose and undertake wellness tourism in Bali apart from the various types of wellness. Based on these results, it can be interpreted that the natural beauty of Bali is one of the pulling factors that can influence tourists' interest in choosing Bali as a suitable place for wellness tourism (27,28).

CONCLUSION

Pull factors and push factors for tourists in choosing wellness tourism in Bali Eling

Spirit gets a high score, so that both factors are both in the high category and for founders of communities or institutions operating in the health tourism sector, they should increase the types of wellness offered so that it is more varied and offered at affordable prices. This can attract tourists and local residents to choose and carry out various types of wellness tourism in Bali.

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